

TOPIC: " QUALITY OF PRIVATE SCHOOLS."

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Abstract

This article highlights the quality and advantages of private schools. Overall, private schools have developed significantly in recent years in our country. Currently, education holds great importance. Schools are also improving the education system through their quality. In this regard, private schools are far ahead. Private schools stand out for their education system, their selection of highly qualified teachers, and their achievements. The salaries paid to teachers and the high cost but quality of private schools set them apart. The size of the classrooms and their brightness also make a difference.

Key words: private school, quality ,salaries, education system.

Introduction

In recent years, a lot of private institutions have been opened. These include schools, universities, and kindergartens. But this means that not all of them are of high quality and may not meet the requirements. Therefore, we will now talk about the quality of private schools. Everyone has a different understanding of private school. The example is good for some and bad for others. Many people say that private schools are attended by educated children and they all study for money. Basically both schools are the same. The quality of private schools is much better than public schools. Also, private schools have qualified teachers and have enough equipment and rooms. Also, the monthly salary of teachers working in a private school is higher. Also, the number of students in private schools is less, while the teacher gives time to all students in the lesson. According to the article, the budget of private schools is also higher. That is, private schools have higher income than public schools. According to Tooley, the choice of private schools is the reason for parents, because nowadays many parents are choosing private schools. Because they are demanding good education for the money they have spent. They want their children to study well so that they do not suffer in the future, and they want qualified teachers to teach their children. Also, the reason for the strong demand for private schools is the fact that there are few children in the classrooms, the teachers are well prepared for the lesson, and the students' attention to the lesson plays an important role.

Literature review

The article "The Feasibility of Realizing the Right to Education" notes that some budget private schools have demonstrated the ability to provide quality education at very low salaries for teachers. Pankaj Jain and Ravindra X Dholakia have provocatively argued that the fundamental right to education, which can be read as a fundamental right to "quality" education, can only be economically viable if the state systematically cooperates with private providers. may be useful can be achieved segment of primary education and focuses its efforts more. (EPW, June 20, 2009). According to Tooley, there are two main sources of information that he uses to evaluate "school quality." First, based on the parent's reasons for choosing the school government or private school. Here, they downplay the attractiveness of English-medium education offered by private schools, preferring instead to interpret parents' preference for (English-medium) private schools as evidence of their (higher) quality assessment.(2009). The second is a survey of a long list of metrics and proxies of quality." Parents part emphasizing on the importance of private schools' syllabus, schools' environment and facilities when selecting to enroll their children in private schools."(Noor Alyani Yaacob, Mariana Mohamed Osman, Syahirah Bachok ,2014). Avram, S. and Dronkers J. (2010) agreed that the qualities of private schools which are often chosen over the public schools can be the guiding principles when improving the public sector schools. This can be due to the establishment of high quality private schools which were originally set to attract the children of affluent families and intelligent students. Whilst small in numbers, private schools are nevertheless similar to public schools. The main distinctive advantages of private schools are that they are more independent and self-sustained. Parents are motivated to select a school given the stringent selection of students by that particular schools and prepared it as a challenge to enroll their own children. Thapa (2013) finding that, in Nepal, higher teacher qualifications on their own do not significantly impact learning; however, when interacted with class size, there is a significant relationship, particularly in private schools. These findings suggest that teacher qualifications can matter, in conditions where teachers are motivated to perform, and where the classroom environment allows for adequate learning opportunities. Overall, the rigorous research tends to show positive effects in fovarour of private school performance2 (Alderman, Orazem, & Paterno, 2001; Bold, Kimenyi, Mwabu, & Sandefur, 2013; Muralidharan & Sundararaman, 2015; Tooley, Bao, Dixon, & Merrield, 2011).However, in some cases, private schools perform on par with

public schools (Azam, Kingdon,6 D. R. BAUM ET AL. & Wu, 2016), and in a small number of studies, public schools outperform their private competitors (Lassibille & Tan, 2001; Lassibille, Tan, & Sumra, 2000).

Findings

- Demand for Private Schools: Most parents choose private education.
- Teacher Salaries: Private school teachers earn higher salaries.

References:

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